

Detailed Study Procedure

Paper: “Tales from the Trenches: Expectations and Challenges from Practice for Code Review in the Generative AI Era”

Authors: Nicole Davila, Jorge Melegati, Igor Wiese

Year: 2024

The need/motivations

- The increasing popularity of generative AI and its impact on software development. e.g., [“Generative AI for Software Practitioners” by Ebert and Louridas \(IEEE Software, 2023\)](#)
- We already have initial evidence these tools are and will influence software development. We still do not know to what extent, e.g., [“Taking Flight with Copilot: Early insights and opportunities of AI-powered pair-programming tools” by Bird et al. \(ACM Queue, 2022\)](#)
- There are recent code review’s SLR/SM that cover the traditional literature.
 - “A Systematic Literature Review and Taxonomy of Modern Code Review” by Davila and Nunes (2021) and “Modern Code Reviews - A Survey of Literature and Practice” by Badampudi et al. (2023)
- “GL provides “current” perspectives and complements gaps of the formal literature [25].” (Garousi et al., 2019, p. 108)

Goal: Our main goal is to investigate what has been discussed about generative AI technologies in the context.

1. Document Search

1.1. Search tool

We decided to search **Google** web search engine.

1.1.1. Reasoning

A popular tool in other GLR studies:

- V. Garousi, M. Felderer, and M. V. Mäntylä, “Guidelines for including grey literature and conducting multivocal literature reviews in software engineering,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 106, pp. 101–121, Feb. 2019. (Journal)

- J. Melegati, E. Guerra, e X. Wang, “Understanding Hypotheses Engineering in Software Startups through a Gray Literature Review”, Information and Software Technology, vol. 133, p. 106465, May 2021. (Journal)

1.1.2. Threat

A possible threat is the existence of relevant documents to our study topic not retrieved by the Google search engine. Nevertheless, we based our decision on the existence of other published studies, suggesting the reliability of using Google as a good option.

1.2. Search string

We defined the search string as **“code review” AND (“generative AI” OR “generative artificial intelligence” OR “ChatGPT” OR “Copilot”)**.

1.2.1. Reasoning

The most recent systematic mapping of code review research (Badampudi et al. (2023)) defined the following keywords for the search string (“[...] combining each keyword with a logical “OR” operation and adding a wildcard operator (*). ”)

- code review
- patch accept
- commit review
- pull request
- modern code inspect

We understand that “patch accept”, “pull request”, and “modern code inspect” return many documents unrelated to the code review practice, burdening the GL review. The remaining terms are more likely to be used by practitioners when referring to code review.

We also followed the topic of the special issue: “generative AI” OR “generative artificial intelligence”. With the terms related to code review mentioned above, we had an initial search string. Then, we checked the possible string combinations.

- Procedure: Testing Search Strings
 - a. Chrome browser on an anonymous tab.
 - b. <https://www.google.com/>
 - c. Inform search string
 - d. Limit of results per page: 100
 - e. Using SEOquake plugin: Export CSV (only first page)
 - f. Check the first 10 results: Is it related to the scope of the study? Is there noise?

- Result of testing:

	String	# Results	# Checked	Noise?	% Noise
T1	"code review" AND "generative AI"	8 760 000	10	3	30%
T2	"code review" AND "artificial intelligence"	596 000	10	2	20%
T3	"patch accept" AND "generative AI"	5	9	9	100%
T4	"patch accept" AND "artificial intelligence"	13	10	10	100%
T5	"commit review" AND "generative AI"	16	10	8	80%
T6	"commit review" AND "artificial intelligence"	68	10	10	100%
T7	"pull request" AND "generative AI"	90	10	8	80%
T8	"pull request" AND "artificial intelligence"	257 000	10	4	40%
T9	"modern code inspect" AND "generative AI"	None			
T10	"modern code inspect" AND "artificial intelligence"	2	6	4	67%
T11	"code review" AND ("generative AI" OR "generative artificial intelligence" OR "ChatGPT" OR "Copilot")	382	10	2	20%

1.2.2. Threat

As our investigation focuses on generative AI in code reviews, we work with two topics, and a possible threat is the terms we select to find documents related to these topics. As a mitigation strategy, we test several combinations of the search string, as shown above. We evaluate the first ten results regarding the amount of noise, i.e., the number of returned hits that do not match the scope of our study. We then selected the terms that produced less noise, which led to the search string used in our review.

1.3. Search execution

We performed the search on the international site of Google in October 2023, obtaining 382 results. Our search procedure:

- Chrome browser on an anonymous tab.
- <https://www.google.com/>
- Inform search string
- Using SEOquake plugin: Export CSV (all results)

2. Document Selection

2.1. Selection criteria

2.1.1. Agreement Level

We started our selection phase without a well-established selection criteria set. Each of the authors has a different background, so we looked to verify our agreement level. In this step, we only evaluate the inclusion criteria: "The document is about generative AI in the code review" (true or yes if the research agrees with the inclusion of the document in our review).

Document	IW	ND	JM
1	TRUE	TRUE	Yes
2	TRUE	TRUE	?
3	TRUE	TRUE	?
4	TRUE	TRUE	?
5	TRUE	TRUE	?
6	TRUE	TRUE	No
7	TRUE	TRUE	Yes
8	TRUE	FALSE	No
9	TRUE	FALSE	No
10	FALS E	FALSE	No
11	TRUE	TRUE	?
12	TRUE	TRUE	Yes
13	TRUE	TRUE	?
14	FALS E	FALSE	No
15	TRUE	FALSE	No
16	TRUE	TRUE	?
17	TRUE	TRUE	Yes
18	TRUE	TRUE	?
19	TRUE	TRUE	Yes*
20	TRUE	TRUE	?

After this individual evaluation, we achieved only 35% agreement. We discussed the disagreement cases, refining our selection criteria based on the following decisions:

- Take a definition of the code review process and adopt it as a guideline to decide whether a document is related to the practice or not: Some documents in this initial analysis broadly compare generative AI tools, not focusing on MCR (or just mentioning it as an example). We refined our selection criteria to focus on

publications of generative AI in the modern code review practice as characterized by literature, i.e., a changed-based, lightweight, flexible, regular, tool-based, and asynchronous code review.

- From this follows a refinement of the inclusion criteria: IC1: The document is about the adoption of generative AI explicitly for the code review process (a specific step or the whole process); IC2: The document is about a tool exploring generative AI to explicitly support the code review process (a specific step or the whole process).
 - We also defined our exclusion criteria as:
 - EC1: Not written in English.
 - EC2: Not text-based content (i.e., videos or slide presentations).
 - Reasoning: Focused on text-based publications to make the process feasible.
 - EC3: Duplicate content.
 - EC4: The document is a forum or group discussion thread.
 - Reasoning: We observed that forums and group discussions were (i) shorter than blog posts without a deeper presentation of the idea and (ii) simply presenting the opinion without discussing arguments or showing pieces of evidence to support that opinion.
 - EC5: The document is the homepage of a popular AI-based tool, such as GitHub Copilot or ChatGPT.
 - EC6: The document is about using generative AI for code review, but the proposed approach takes as input a whole Git repository, folder, or file.
 - Reasoning: Modern code review convergent practice refers to small code changes.
 - EC7: The document is unavailable.

Using the refined criteria, the same subset of results was reassessed:

Document	Nicole	Jorge
1	TRUE	TRUE
2	TRUE	TRUE
3	TRUE	TRUE
4	TRUE	TRUE
5	TRUE	TRUE
6	FALSE	FALSE
7	TRUE	TRUE
8	FALSE	FALSE
9	FALSE	FALSE
10	FALSE	FALSE
11	TRUE	TRUE
12	TRUE	TRUE

13	TRUE	TRUE
14	FALSE	FALSE
15	FALSE	FALSE
16	TRUE	TRUE
17	TRUE	TRUE
18	TRUE	TRUE
19	FALSE	FALSE
20	FALSE	FALSE

We then achieved total agreement.

2.1.2. Filtering

Nicole accessed and inspected the first 191 (our stopping criteria, to make the process feasible) out of 382 results, following the selection criteria below. We included documents that match at least one IC and no EC. The content of the assessed links was saved in PDF format. Details of this filtering are available in a spreadsheet of our supplementary material. The resulting list of primary documents considered in our study is available at the end of this document.

3. Data Analysis

We conducted a thematic analysis using a qualitative approach. We followed the guidelines below, performing as steps: extract data, code data, translate code into themes, and create a model of higher-order themes.

[1]

D. S. Cruzes e T. Dyba, "Recommended Steps for Thematic Synthesis in Software Engineering", em *2011 International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement*, Banff, AB: IEEE, set. 2011, p. 275–284.

3.1. Data extraction

Nicole read the included documents to get immersed in their content. It was extracted (when available): Title, Author, Date, and Author's background. We also identified the possibility of extracting the **document type** as a description of the context instead of the **study type** normally applicable to traditional literature. We found the following document types:

- Solution Proposal: Documents proposing a solution proposal using examples or descriptions to argue its effectiveness.
- Opinion study: Documents expressing a personal opinion of the author(s) (good or bad aspects) or how they consider things should be done.
- Experience studies: Documents reporting how something has been used in practice.

- Validation research: Documents present initial empirical evidence regarding the solution's effectiveness.

3.2. Coding

Nicole extracted excerpts from the document and coded them using an inductive approach where codes emerged from the data. The resulting codebook, with codes, their descriptions, and frequency counter is available in our supplementary material.

3.2.1. Threat

Only Nicole conducted the coding, which may threaten our study. As a mitigation strategy and to provide a sound classification, we performed a checkpoint. From 42 included documents, 16 were randomly selected for Jorge and Igor to evaluate the data extraction. Each of them checked 8 documents:

- Jorge checked the documents with the following ID: 3, 11, 16, 22, 47, 48, 96, 124.
- Igor checked the documents with the following ID: 4, 5, 7, 25, 27, 28, 32, 80.

After their individual evaluation, all researchers discuss disagreements.

3.3. Refinement

During data analysis, we continuously explored the relationship between our codes and grouped them into categories, sub-categories, and high-order themes. For instance, a code referring to better cost-benefit and a code referring to increased quality were considered related, as both refer to the benefits of using generative AI in code review. Thus, we group these two codes together.

When all documents were coded, all researchers compared and analyzed the resulting codebook regarding coherency and consistency, checking if each theme represented one and only one concept with minimal overlapping.

4. List of References of Gray Literature Review

[G1] anc95, Codereview BOT, <https://github.com/anc95/ChatGPT-CodeReview>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).

[G2] A. Rice, D. Rifkin, M. Rothenberg, M. Schaefer, A. Siddiqui, D. Syme, A. Ziegler, Copilot for pull requests, <https://githubnext.com/projects/copilot-for-pull-requests>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).

[G3] C. Picard, Chatgpt: Your new coding buddy for automated code reviews, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/chatgpt-your-new-coding-buddy-automated-code-reviews-caden-picard#:~:text=Enter%20ChatGPT%2C%20a%20language%20model,sneaky%20bugs%20that%20s lip%20through.>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).

- [G4]** M. Vizard, Integral makes generative ai code review tool open source, <https://devops.com/integral-makes-generative-ai-code-review-tool-open-source/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G5]** Metabob, Ai code review for refactoring and debugging, <https://metabob.com/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G6]** L. Zim, Chatgpt pr code review, <https://gpt3demo.com/apps/chatgpt-pr-code-review>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G7]** K. Videlov, N. Galaiko, codereview.gpt, <https://github.com/sturdy-dev/codereview.gpt>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G8]** A. Espresso, Smarter code reviews with ai: Capitalizing on chatgpt and cr.gpt for enhanced code reviews and pull requests, <https://medium.com/the-ai-espresso/smarter-code-reviews-with-ai-capitalizing-on-chatgpt-and-cr-gpt-bdf02c8c16f6>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G9]** M. Fu, A chatgpt-powered code reviewer bot for open-source projects, <https://www.cncf.io/blog/2023/06/06/a-chatgpt-powered-code-reviewer-bot-for-open-source-projects/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G10]** L. Sciga, Ai code reviewer: Enhancing code review efficiency with chatgpt, <https://www.astrafy.io/articles/ai-code-reviewer-enhancing-code-review-efficiency-with-chatgpt>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G11]** A. Shao, Openai chatgpt code review, <https://github.com/adshao/chatgpt-code-review-action>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G12]** Cirolini, Code review with chatgpt, <https://github.com/marketplace/actions/code-review-with-chatgpt>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G13]** M. Paulsen, Generative ai-enabled compliance for software development, <https://github.blog/2023-04-11-generative-ai-enabled-compliance-for-software-development/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G14]** L. Sobrecueva, Build a project that automates your code review, <https://www.packtpub.com/article-hub/build-a-project-that-automates-your-code-review>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G15]** M. L. Van, Crgpt - code review chatgpt, <https://github.com/minhlucvan/crgpt>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G16]** CodeRabbit, Ai-based pr reviewer and summarizer, <https://github.com/coderabbitai/ai-pr-reviewer>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G17]** M. Huang, Angular code review, <https://www.aiprm.com/prompts/softwareengineering/backend-development/1789497861952770048/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G18]** P. Ni, Automated pull requests reviewing and issues triaging with chatgpt., <https://github.com/feiskyer/ChatGPT-Reviewer>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).

- [G19] F. Dinu, Chatgpt pr code review, <https://github.com/marketplace/actions/chatgpt-pr-code-review>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G20] P. Sullivan, Aaron code review chatgpt plugin tutorial, use cases & prompts, <https://roi hacks.com/aaron-code-review-chatgpt-plugin/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G21] Y. Almeida, Ai code review, <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/21106-ai-code-review>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G22] S. K. Basha, Excited to Share: How to Perform Code Review Using ChatGPT! | LinkedIn, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/excited-share-how-perform-code-review-using-chatgpt-khadar-basha/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G23] F. Zaninotto, Using copilot to review code and fund open-source projects, <https://marmelab.com/blog/2023/02/27/copilot-code-review.html>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G24] S. Vashisth, Leveraging chatgpt for code review. a practical guide., <https://medium.com/@hybridappdev/leveraging-chatgpt-for-code-review-a-practical-guide-f30c44a333ca>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G25] R. Hadari, Streamlining code reviews with generative ai, <https://www.goretro.ai/post/streamlining-code-reviews-with-generative-ai>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G26] B. Ghosh, Generative ai in devsecops, <https://medium.com/@bijit211987/generative-ai-in-devsecops-45816c56a7d0>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G27] C. Dilmegani, Generative ai coding: Top 10+ use cases & 5 tools in 2023, <https://research.aimultiple.com/generative-ai-coding/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G28] M. Mendonca, Using generative ai, amazon bedrock and amazon codeguru to improve code quality and security, <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/devops/using-generative-ai-amazon-bedrock-and-amazon-codeguru-to-improve-code-quality-and-security/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G29] W. Franchin, Top 5 chatgpt uses for developers, <https://medium.com/javarevisited/top-5-chatgpt-uses-for-developers-3afa04960dc7>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G30] S. Maheshwari, Hello folks, are you looking for a way to improve the quality and security of your code?, https://www.linkedin.com/posts/shashank-maheshwari-98b202178_generative-ai-to-improve-and-automate-code-activity-7090006490039656448-ubth, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G31] P. Veitch, Generative ai: A practical guide for software engineers to harness innovative tools, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/generative-ai-practical-guide-software-engineers-harness-paul-veitch/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).

- [G32] A. S. Anjo, Supercharge productivity with generative ai and gitlab duo, <https://about.gitlab.com/blog/2023/07/20/supercharge-productivity-with-gitlab-duo/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G33] S. Das, The power of generative ai: Transforming devops with chatgpt, <https://sandipdas.medium.com/the-power-of-generative-ai-transforming-devops-with-chatgpt-72330d56e4b7>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G34] R. P. Delgado, How to conduct a code review using ai, <https://www.fiverr.com/resources/guides/programming-tech/code-review-using-ai/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G35] Rahul, How to effectively use chatgpt for software development, <https://tecadmin.net/using-chatgpt-for-software-development/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G36] Swimm, Ai code review: How it works and 3 tools you should know, <https://swimm.io/learn/ai-tools-for-developers/ai-code-review-how-it-works-and-3-tools-you-should-know>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G37] R. McColl, On-demand code review with chatgpt, <https://www.nearform.com/blog/on-demand-code-review-with-chatgpt/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G38] Chrisanley, Security code review with chatgpt, <https://research.nccgroup.com/2023/02/09/security-code-review-with-chatgpt/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G39] S. K. Basha, Exciting news! elevate your code review process with chatgpt integration!, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/exciting-news-elevate-your-code-review-process-shaik-khadar-basha>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G40] A.-R. Adl-Tabatabai, S. Badem, A. Chadha, A. Huda, B. Lico, The transformative power of generative ai in software development: Lessons from uber's tech-wide hackathon, <https://www.uber.com/blog/the-transformative-power-of-generative-ai/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G41] M. Bean, Yesterday, i asked chatgpt to do a code review for me., https://www.linkedin.com/posts/beanmarcus_yesterday-i-asked-chatgpt-to-do-a-code-review-activity-7115581129155325954-ER6p, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023).
- [G42] M. Rodriguez, Research: Quantifying github copilot's impact on code quality, <https://github.blog/2023-10-10-research-quantifying-github-copilots-impact-on-code-quality/>, accessed: 2023-10-30 (2023)